

NDAC/LO/061

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RESULTS OF IDT PREPROCESSING SIMULATIONS

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Introduction

This note describes the results of two phase extraction algorithms applied to the IDT counts simulated at ESTEC (April 1985). The first algorithm is a strict ML estimator (truncated however after a single ML iteration); the second is a similar algorithm applied on the binned samples (45 bins). Sample results are given in Tables 1-2, which are written on the format proposed below; the complete results (for 369 observations in 90 frames) have been sent on a tape to S Vaghi.

Input data

The second run of the data described in a letter by Vaghi (1985 April 2) was used; this includes no other error sources besides the Poisson noise.

Signal model

The estimated parameters are:

I_0 = mean count rate (DC component), in Hz

I_1 = amplitude of 1st harmonic, in Hz

I_2 = amplitude of 2nd harmonic, in Hz

p_1 = position (or phase) of 1st harmonic at frame mid-time, in arcsec

p_2 = position (or phase) of 2nd harmonic at frame mid-time, in arcsec

p_0 = weighted mean of p_1 and p_2 , in arcsec.

The signal model is therefore

$$N_\ell \sim I_0 \Delta t + I_1 \Delta t \cos(H_\ell + 2\pi p_1/s) + I_2 \Delta t \cos 2(H_\ell + 2\pi p_2/s) \quad (1)$$

with $\Delta t = 1/1200$ s and $s = 1.208$ arcsec. N_ℓ and H_ℓ are the photon count and reference phase of the ℓ th sample ($\ell = 1$ to 2560 in the frame). The reference phase was computed as

$$H_\ell = 2\pi v(\ell - 1280.5)\Delta t/s \quad (2)$$

with $v = 168.75$ arcsec/s. The phase ambiguity of p_1 and p_2 is resolved by means of the conventions

$$0 \leq p_1 < s \quad (3a)$$

$$|p_2 - p_1| < s/2 \quad (3b)$$

$$I_1, I_2 \geq 0 \quad (3c)$$

The weighted mean is computed as

$$p_0 = w p_1 + (1-w) p_2 \quad (4)$$

with $w = 0.75$.

AlgorithmsReference solution (no binning)

The parameters b_1 to b_5 in

$$N_\ell \sim b_1 + b_2 \cos H_\ell + b_3 \sin H_\ell + b_4 \cos 2H_\ell + b_5 \sin 2H_\ell \quad (5)$$

where estimated in two steps. First, an unweighted least-squares solution was made and used to compute the (approximate) expected counts E_ℓ according to the rhs of (5). Then, a single ML refinement was made in the form of a second least-squares solution, in which the weight of each sample was set to $1/E_\ell$. This gave the final parameters $b_1 - b_5$, the chi-square, and the covariance matrix of the b 's.

Finally, $b_1 - b_5$ were transformed to $I_0, I_1, I_2, p_0, p_1, p_2$ and the corresponding variances were obtained from the covariance matrix.

Binned solution

The interval $[0, 2\pi[$ of the reference phase (modulo 2π) was divided into 45 equal bins ($m = 0$ to 44). For each bin the number of samples (w_m) and mean count ($\bar{N}_m$) were computed, and the following model applied:

$$\bar{N}_m \sim b_1 + b_2 \cos H_m + b_3 \sin H_m + b_4 \cos 2H_m + b_5 \sin 2H_m \quad (\text{weight } w_m) \quad (6)$$

in which H_m is the reference phase at the centre of bin m . The estimation of $b_1 - b_5$ is exactly as above, except that the weights used for each bin is now w_m in the first ("unweighted") solution, and w_m/E_m in the second (ML refinement). Transformation to I_0 etc is the same as before.

Output format

The results in Table 1 and 2 (and on the tape) are arranged with five lines per observation, viz.:

(empty line)

#k	i	nacc	I_0	I_1	I_2	p_0	p_1	p_2
			σ_{I0}	σ_{I1}	σ_{I2}	σ_{p0}	σ_{p1}	σ_{p2}
						Δp_0	Δp_1	Δp_2
					t1	$\Delta p_0 / \sigma_{p0}$	$\Delta p_1 / \sigma_{p1}$	$\Delta p_2 / \sigma_{p2}$

k is the frame number (with negative sign for an observation in f-field), i is the star number and $nacc$ the number of accepted samples. σ are the formal mean errors of the respective parameters and Δp the difference between the estimated p and true p (estimated - true). $t1$ is the transformed chi-square variable

$$t1 = [(\chi^2/\nu)^{1/3} - (1 - 2/9\nu)](9\nu/2)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

which is approximately unit normal if χ^2 has the chi-square distribution with ν degrees of freedom. Thus, $t1 \geq 3.5$ would indicate excess noise with respect to the 5-parameter model (1). The last three items are the actual errors divided by the formal mean errors; these should be unit normal if the errors behave as expected.

The present definition of signal parameters, units, and data format may be suitable for comparing the results of different reductions. Only the second line ($\pm k, i, \dots$) is really necessary, however, and the fifth line may contain other statistics than in this example. Moreover, p_0 may refer to the phase estimate of the 3-parameter model instead of the present weighted mean. The actual FORTRAN format used here is:

```

FORMAT(
FORMAT(3I6,3F10.1,3F8.4)
FORMAT(18X,3F10.1,3F8.4)
FORMAT(48X,          3F8.4)
FORMAT(38X, F10.2,3F8.2)

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Analysis of results

Binned solution vs. reference solution

The rms values of the actual errors (Δp_i) are as follows:

solution	$(\Delta p_0)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_1)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_2)_{\text{rms}}$
reference	8.38 mas	8.58 mas	13.22 mas
binned	8.46 mas	8.68 mas	13.27 mas
difference	0.85 mas	0.91 mas	1.23 mas

The bottom line, "difference", gives the rms values of the differences $(\Delta p_i)_{\text{bin}} - (\Delta p_i)_{\text{ref}}$. The noise contribution by the binning is thus of the order of 1 mas, as expected from the preliminary study (NDAC/LO/058).

Error distributions

The rms values of the normalized errors ($\Delta p/\sigma_{p_i}$) are:

solution	$(\Delta p_0/\sigma_{p0})_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_1/\sigma_{p1})_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_2/\sigma_{p2})_{\text{rms}}$
reference	0.9943	0.9857	1.0136
binned	1.0096	0.9998	1.0202

Given the limited size of the sample (369 points $\Rightarrow$ relative uncertainty of 3.7% on rms values), there is no significant deviation from unity. Normal probability plots of the normalized errors (Figs. 1-3) do not suggest any significant bias or deviation from normality.

Distribution of chi-square statistic

The rms values of the transformed χ^2 variable (t_1) are: for the reference solution = 0.9799; for the binned solution = 0.9573. A normal probability plot of t_1 (for binned solution) is shown in Fig. 4. Thus it appears that the chi-square goodness-of-fit indeed follows the chi-square distribution with the appropriate degree of freedom ($\nu = \text{nacc}-5$ for the reference solution; $\nu = 40$ for the binned solution).

Correlation between β_5 and β_3

In NDAC/MSSL/008 a certain (negative) correlation was observed between the signal parameters

$$\beta_3 = \text{ATAN2}(-b_3, b_2) = 2\pi p_1/s \quad (7a)$$

and

$$\beta_5 = [(b_2^2 - b_3^2) b_5 - 2b_2 b_3 b_4] / (b_2^2 + b_3^2)^{3/2} = \frac{I_2}{I_1} \sin[4\pi(p_1 - p_2)/s] \quad (7b)$$

The correlation is seen in plots of $\Delta\beta_5$ versus $\Delta\beta_3$, which presumably means the deviations of the observed β_5 and β_3 values from the true ones, i.e.

$$\Delta\beta_3 = 2\pi\Delta p_1/s \quad (8a)$$

$$\Delta\beta_5 = \beta_5 \quad (8b)$$

Fig. 5 is a plot of $\Delta\beta_5$ versus $\Delta\beta_3$ computed from the binned solution according to (7)-(8). The sample correlation coefficient is +0.322, i.e. apparently opposite to the one reported in NDAC/MSSL/008.

The theoretical correlation is readily obtained from the covariance matrix, and is found to be about 0.32 (as an average of the first 16 observations; there is a rather large scatter between observations, but the correlation is always positive). The observed correlation thus appears to be entirely consistent with theoretical expectations and does not indicate any defect in the simulated data.

On the choice of weight factor

The (constant) weight factor $w = 0.75$ for computing the mean phase between the two harmonics was chosen to be close to the theoretical optimal value (minimizing the variance of the weighted mean phase). The optimal weight factor for any observation can be calculated from the covariance matrix (cf. NDAC/LO/038). It is remarkable that the improvement compared to the first harmonic is so little, only about 2.5% on the mean errors.

I tried also to use the weight factor $w = M_1^2 / (M_1^2 + 4M_2^2) \simeq 0.66$ suggested by MATRA, but in this case the actual dispersion of the mean phase was in fact slightly larger than that of the first harmonic. Applying a 3-parameter signal model, or constraining the 5-parameter model (as done by the Location Estimator) is more or less equivalent to choosing an optimal weight factor for each observation, and should give a slight improvement over p_0 as it is calculated here.

Table 1. Sample output of reference (unbinned) section; first 5 frames. 5(11)

±frame	star	nacc	I_0	I_1	I_2	P_0	P_1	P_2	
			m.e.	m.e.	m.e.	m.e.	m.e.	m.e.	
						ΔP_0	ΔP_1	ΔP_2	
						t_1	$\Delta P_0/\sigma_{P_0}$	$\Delta P_1/\sigma_{P_1}$	$\Delta P_2/\sigma_{P_2}$
1	56	512	5955.9	4427.9	1235.7	.5158	.5149	.5184	
			118.2	174.2	155.0	.0069	.0068	.0121	
						-1.51	-.0010	-.0018	
							-.27	.14	
1	55	1024	373.8	280.0	65.4	.5083	.5071	.5120	
			20.9	30.7	27.4	.0206	.0194	.0403	
							.0151	.0139	
						-.36	.73	.72	
								.47	
1	54	512	6090.0	4690.9	1689.7	.9367	.9340	.9446	
			119.5	178.5	155.7	.0060	.0063	.0088	
							-.0101	-.0028	
						1.03	-1.69	-2.01	
								-.25	
-1	719	512	6093.1	4501.1	1537.8	.2056	.2040	.2105	
			119.5	178.1	156.9	.0063	.0067	.0098	
							-.0048	-.0064	
						2.23	-.76	-.97	
								.01	
2	56	384	5981.4	4390.9	1576.7	.5316	.5329	.5279	
			136.7	203.8	179.4	.0073	.0078	.0110	
							-.0040	-.0027	
						-1.00	-.54	-.35	
								-.70	
2	55	1024	351.5	229.9	100.7	.5066	.5091	.4992	
			20.3	30.5	26.9	.0193	.0216	.0257	
							-.0055	-.0030	
						-1.61	-.29	-.14	
								-.50	
2	54	512	5802.3	4259.1	1437.0	.9607	.9570	.9718	
			116.6	173.6	153.0	.0065	.0069	.0102	
							-.0049	-.0086	
						1.53	-.75	-1.25	
								.60	
-2	719	544	5979.9	4459.1	1608.4	.2065	.2063	.2071	
			114.9	171.5	150.3	.0060	.0064	.0090	
							.0018	.0016	
						-1.49	.29	.25	
								.26	
2	53	96	5962.9	4536.3	2012.3	.5434	.5455	.5371	
			272.7	412.2	357.7	.0130	.0145	.0169	
							-.0049	-.0028	
						.68	-.38	-.20	
								-.66	
3	54	768	6115.6	4515.6	1471.0	.9787	.9757	.9877	
			97.8	145.3	128.4	.0052	.0055	.0084	
							-.0065	.0033	
						-.47	1.23	.64	
								1.85	
-3	719	640	6292.8	4485.1	1737.9	.1970	.1983	.1933	
			108.6	162.6	143.1	.0055	.0060	.0079	
							-.0020	-.0008	
						.44	-.36	-.13	
								-.73	

Table 2. Sample output of the binned solution (first 3 frames).

6(11)

#frame	star	nacc	I_0 m.e.	I_1 m.e.	I_2 m.e.	P_0 m.e.	P_1 m.e.	P_2 m.e.
						Δp_0 $\Delta p_0/\sigma_{p0}$	Δp_1 $\Delta p_1/\sigma_{p1}$	Δp_2 $\Delta p_2/\sigma_{p2}$
					t1			
1	56	512	5956.8 118.2	4432.9 174.1	1246.2 154.6	.5176 .0069 .0009	.5165 .0068 -.0002	.5210 .0120 .0043
					-.44	.13	-.04	.36
1	55	1024	373.3 20.9	279.0 30.5	63.6 27.4	.5076 .0210 .0143	.5063 .0195 .0130	.5114 .0414 .0182
					.19	.68	.67	.44
1	54	512	6100.4 119.7	4702.8 178.9	1663.9 155.7	.9375 .0060 -.0093	.9349 .0063 -.0118	.9453 .0090 -.0015
					-.30	-1.55	-1.87	-.17
-1	719	512	6075.0 119.1	4469.8 176.9	1511.4 156.9	.2053 .0064 -.0052	.2035 .0067 -.0070	.2106 .0099 .0002
					-1.55	-.81	-1.04	.02
2	56	384	5981.6 136.8	4392.3 203.8	1564.7 178.8	.5324 .0074 -.0032	.5339 .0078 -.0017	.5280 .0111 -.0076
					1.26	-.43	-.22	-.68
2	55	1024	350.8 20.2	228.7 30.4	101.9 26.9	.5064 .0193 -.0057	.5089 .0217 -.0032	.4990 .0254 -.0131
					.98	-.29	-.15	-.52
2	54	512	5812.8 116.8	4274.6 174.3	1441.6 153.4	.9611 .0065 -.0046	.9574 .0068 -.0083	.9721 .0102 .0064
					.49	-.71	-1.21	.63
-2	719	544	5961.8 114.5	4423.2 170.6	1595.1 150.5	.2068 .0061 .0021	.2068 .0065 .0021	.2068 .0090 .0021
					-.77	.35	.32	.23
2	53	96	6008.2 275.0	4577.7 417.4	2021.9 360.5	.5446 .0128 -.0037	.5465 .0143 -.0018	.5389 .0169 -.0095
					1.11	-.29	-.13	-.56
3	54	768	6101.6 97.5	4491.4 144.6	1454.7 128.3	.9786 .0053 .0063	.9756 .0055 .0033	.9875 .0085 .0153
					-.09	1.19	.60	1.81
-3	719	640	6304.5 108.8	4497.3 163.2	1744.4 143.4	.1975 .0055 -.0015	.1986 .0060 -.0004	.1943 .0079 -.0047
					-.17	-.27	-.07	-.59

NORMAL PROBABILITY PLOT FOR $\Delta p_0/m.e.$

Fig. 1. Probability plot (on a normal grid) of the actual error of the weighted mean phase, divided by its formal mean error ($\Delta p_0/\sigma_{p_0}$). If the plotted values (ordinate) follow the centred unit normal p_0 distribution, $\Delta p_0/\sigma_{p_0} \sim N(0,1)$, then the points should lie approximately on a straight line with slope = 1 through the origin.

(369 points; binned solution.)

NORMAL PROBABILITY PLOT FOR $\Delta p_1/m.e.$

Fig. 2. Same as Fig. 1 but for the phase error of the first harmonic, $\Delta p_1/\sigma_{p1}$. (369 points; binned solution.)

NORMAL PROBABILITY PLOT FOR $dp_2/m.e.$

Fig. 3. Same as Fig. 1 but for the phase error of the second harmonic, $\Delta p_2/\sigma_{p2}$. (369 points; binned solution.)

NORMAL PROBABILITY PLOT FOR t_1

Fig. 4. Probability plot of the transformed goodness-of-fit statistic t_1 (Eqn. 6). (369 points; binned solution.)

CORRELATION beta5 VS. beta3 (BINNED SOLUTION)

Fig. 5. Correlation between $\Delta\beta_5$ and $\Delta\beta_3$. The variables have been normalized according to their respective mean errors.